

Do We Have to Adapt to a Life with COVID-19 as a Permanent ‘Guest’?

Dr. Hicham Bouabe

Can the ongoing global vaccination and public health measures lead to successful containment of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and eradication of the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)? Or will COVID-19 become a recurrent (‘seasonal’) or permanent infectious disease?

In order to answer this question, we should have a look at previous viral epidemics, understand the factors that have led to their successful containment and eradication, and examine whether such factors are available in the case of COVID-19.

How the SARS epidemic of 2003 could be contained and SARS-CoV-1 eradicated?

On 16 November 2002, a 45-year-old man in Foshan City in South China became ill with fever and respiratory symptoms. He has been retrospectively identified as the first case of a new viral respiratory illness that has been named by the World Health Organization (WHO) as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), and the virus caused this disease was named SARS-Coronavirus (SARS-CoV). Since 2020, SARS-CoV was renamed as SARS-CoV-1.

Only few months after the announcement of the global outbreak of SARS, which resulted in the infection of over 8,000 people from 29 different countries and the death of 774 people, the WHO declared on 5 July 2003 that the human chains of SARS virus transmission appeared to have been broken everywhere in the world, and thus SARS has been contained. Since late 2004, SARS-CoV-1 has been widely considered as eradicated in humans.

Interestingly, the containment of SARS was realized without the development/contribution of vaccines.

Three key factors have led to the containment of SARS and subsequent eradication of SARS-CoV-1:

1. Public health measures including isolation of suspected patients

The public health measures that prevent the transmission of the virus from infected people to non-infected people. These included active detection and isolation of people with SARS, tracing and quarantine of their contacts and all suspected patients until SARS was ruled out, social distancing, and community quarantine.

However, isolation measures can be successful in preventing transmission, only if infection cases are detected and isolated before the onset of viral shedding (viral release) or at least before the onset of peak viral shedding, and thus before the virus can be transmitted. This was possible in the case of SARS, because of a critical intrinsic feature of SARS-CoV-1, which represents the second key factor for SARS containment.

2. SARS contagious only when it becomes symptomatic:

SARS-CoV-1 has a relatively short incubation period of 2 to ~5 days. The incubation period is the time a virus requires to show symptoms of the disease after an individual is infected. And the viral loads of SARS-CoV-1 peaked at 6–11 days after onset of illness. It was reported that the amount of virus shed from the respiratory secretions, urine, and faeces of infected patients in the first few days of illness is usually low or undetectable, and there have been no reports of transmission of SARS-CoV-1 before the onset of symptoms or in asymptomatic cases⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. This enabled early detection and isolation of infected people before they can shed and transmit the virus to other people.

3. Deleterious/attenuating mutation:

The third key factor that helped to contain SARS and led to the eradication of SARS-CoV-1, is a deleterious attenuating 'fixed' mutation acquired during the early stages of human-to-human transmission (apparently during the early phase of the SARS epidemic) and remained as virus replication and transmission continued. The attenuating mutation is a 29 nucleotide deletion occurred in the viral genome, in a region called Orf8 that encodes a small polypeptide, and was present in most isolates

from humans during the epidemic. The truncation of ORF8 (the 29 nucleotide deletion) decreased the replication of SARS-CoV-1 up to 23-fold⁽⁵⁾. The SARS epidemic in 2003 would have taken a more severe course if this mutation hadn't occurred.

How Smallpox could be eradicated?

Smallpox is an infectious disease caused by *Variola virus*. There are two forms of the *Variola virus*, the less common and relatively mild *Variola minor* and the most common and deadlier *Variola major*.

Smallpox is among the most lethal of all diseases, estimated to have killed more than 300 million people from 1900 until its eradication in 1980, with 20 million cases and 2 million deaths in 1967 alone, the year in which the Intensified Smallpox Eradication Program started. *Variola major* had a death rate of about 30%, and the less common form, *Variola minor*, had a lethality rate of about 1%. Most people who survived the smallpox, had distinctive residual pockmarks (scars), and some were left blind.

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The eradication of the smallpox was realised through massive global vaccination campaigns, using live 'attenuated' *Vaccinia virus*. *Vaccinia virus* is an animal virus that belongs to the family of Poxviruses which includes also the *Variola virus* that causes the smallpox in human. The *Vaccinia virus* is harmless for humans, but because of its genetic similarity to the threatening *Variola virus*, it induces protective immunity also against the later.

The last reported case of smallpox was in October 1977. In 1980 WHO declared smallpox eradicated. It is the first infectious disease that has been eradicated. Only two other infectious diseases can be considered as eradicated, the veterinary viral disease rinderpest (cattle plague) in 2011, and SARS in 2004.

Key factors that contributed to the successful eradication of smallpox

The global vaccination campaign that started in 1967 could succeed in eradicating the smallpox only because of key features of smallpox virus.

1. Isolation of patients before smallpox becomes transmissible:

Smallpox was transmissible only when the patients showed symptoms and were anyway too sick and thus had to stay in bed. In addition, smallpox spreads mainly among close contacts. The initial symptoms (from day 2-4 after infection) include high fever, head and body aches and sometimes vomiting. During this phase, smallpox was sometimes and slightly contagious. In subsequent stage, the symptoms include rash and small red spots on the tongue and in the mouth. The spots change into sores that break open and spread large amounts of the virus. The sores become then pustules, which are sharply raised, usually round and firm to the touch, like peas under the skin. During this stage, smallpox was most transmissible.

Because of the visible and clear characteristic symptoms of smallpox, it was easy to identify and isolate infected people before they could transmit the virus to non-infected people.

2. Low mutation rate of the smallpox virus

Smallpox virus (*Variola virus*) genome consists of double-stranded (ds) DNA. Unlike RNA viruses, DNA viruses have lower mutation rates. And within DNA viruses, the dsDNA viruses have lower mutation rates compared to single-stranded (ss) DNA viruses.

Smallpox virus has an estimated mutation rate of $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6}$ substitutions per nucleotide per year (sub/nuc/yr). For comparison, RNA viruses have higher mutation rates, such as human immunodeficiency virus (HIV): $\sim 1 \times 10^{-2}$ sub/nuc/yr, poliovirus: $\sim 1 \times 10^{-3}$ sub/nuc/yr, influenza A virus: 1.43 to 11.62×10^{-3} sub/nuc/yr, and preliminary data suggest for SARS-CoV-2 a mutation rate of 0.8 - 6.58×10^{-3} sub/nuc/yr^(6,7).

Because of its low mutation rate, smallpox virus has very low chance for antigenic drift. Antigenic drift is a genetic variation resulting from accumulation of mutations in the viral genes encoding proteins (e.g. surface proteins) against which immunity raised upon natural infection or vaccination.

Thus, the smallpox virus can't usually escape the immune response in form of mutated strains. Vaccine-elicited immunity is, subsequently, effective in neutralising the virus and break its transmission.

3. Human is the only reservoir for smallpox virus

There is no animal reservoir of the smallpox virus, so that the virus can't escape into it and re-infect humans once their immunity against the virus is eased.

Furthermore, the virus can be carried by humans only for a short period. Thus, in order to survive, smallpox has to spread continuously from one person to the next.

The essential sustained transmission, however, was effectively broken by vaccination, which resulted in eradication of the virus.

Unlike SARS-CoV-1 and Smallpox, SARS-CoV-2 doesn't appear to be predestined for eradication

The table below summarizes the most important characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 in comparison to smallpox and SARS viruses.

	Smallpox virus	SARS-CoV-1	SARS-CoV-2
Asymptomatic Transmission	NO	NO	YES
Effectiveness of isolation measures	Very high	Very high	Low
Basic reproduction number (R_0)* (8)	~6.87 (9)	~0.95 (10)	~2.87 (10)
Antigenic drift	So far Unknown	So far Unknown	Yes
Mutation rate (sub/nuc/yr**)	~1 x10 ⁻⁶	7.8 x 10 ⁻³	0.8 - 6.58 x 10 ⁻³ ***
Deleterious mutations	So far Unknown	Yes	Unknown
Escape mutations	NO	NO	YES
Non-human reservoir	NO	YES	YES
Vaccine available	YES	NO	YES
Vaccine formulation update to be tailored against most recent and common circulating strains	NO	Not applicable	YES

*The basic reproduction number (R_0), pronounced “R zero”, is intended to be an indicator of the transmissibility of infectious agents. R_0 of an infection is the expected number of persons directly infected by one person in a population where all individuals are susceptible to infection (a population where the individuals are not immunized - naturally or through vaccination – against the disease). For example, if R_0 is 3, then one person is expected to infect three new people.

**sub/nuc/yr = substitutions per nucleotide per year

*** preliminary data

(8), (9), (10): see references below. (Table created by DR Hicham Bouabe)

According to the above mentioned characteristics that helped to contain/eradicate smallpox and SARS, there are factor combinations that need to be met, in order to be able to contain COVID-19 and eradicate SARS-CoV-2.

For instance:

- The disease can be contained, even without a vaccine, if the virus would spread only after onset of symptoms, enabling active early detection and isolation of infected people before they become contagious. However, this is not the case of SARS-CoV-2, as asymptomatic infected people have transmitted the virus. Isolation of infected patients often happens only after onset of symptoms, when the patients have usually already spread the virus to others.

- Vaccines can contribute to the containment of the disease and eradication of the virus, only if, on one hand, they show high effectiveness, and on the other hand the mutation rate of the virus is low, restricting the occurrence of genetic drift. However, SARS-CoV-2 has shown a high mutation rate of $0.8 - 6.58 \times 10^{-3}$ sub/nuc/yr, in the range of the mutation rates of influenza A virus, the causative agent of the seasonal flu epidemics. So far, more than 5000 distinct SARS-CoV-2 genetic variants have been identified, the majority of the them (~3000) are missense mutations (point mutations in which a single nucleotide change that results in a codon that codes for a different amino acid compared to the initial strain). Over 400 of the missense mutations are located in the gene coding for the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2⁽¹¹⁻¹⁶⁾. As current vaccines target the spike protein based on a genome sequence of the initial SARS-CoV-2 strain, subsequent mutations in the spike protein may reduce their efficacy (efficacy of the current vaccines) or completely escape the vaccine-elicited immunity. Indeed, at least three SARS-CoV-2 variants (B.1.351, P.1 and B.1.1.7+E484K) with mutations in the spike protein have shown reduced or loss of neutralisation by vaccine-elicited antibodies⁽¹¹⁻¹⁶⁾.

Antibodies against spike protein

- There are many animal reservoir of SARS-CoV-2, so that the virus can escape into them and re-infect humans ones their immunity against the virus is eased.

The above mentioned characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 have a knock-on effect on the outcome of the current COVID-19 pandemic. The causal sequence is as follows:

- ❖ The human chains of SARS-CoV-2 transmission can't be broken only by quarantine/isolation measures.
- ❖ In addition, as SARS-CoV-2 is clearly prone to mutations and transmissions of SARS-CoV-2 from a human to another occur frequently, it is very likely that new variants or strains of SARS-CoV-2 (escape mutants) might emerge with the ability to escape the natural or vaccine-elicited immunity and to resist current treatments with monoclonal antibodies and antiviral drugs.
- ❖ Moreover, it is very likely that the emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 escape mutants can be further amplified by increased population immunity (following natural infection or vaccination), because population immunity is known to drive escape mutations, especially in infectious agents prone for mutations, as is the case for SARS-CoV-2.

Taken together, it is most likely that resistive escape mutants of SARS-CoV-2 may emerge frequently with the ability to sustain transmission within the population. Thus it is very likely that COVID-19 will become a recurrent (seasonal) or even permanent (over the whole year) epidemic infectious disease (maybe with lower incidences in spring and summer). This in turn will demand regular update of the vaccine formulation and antiviral drugs, in order to be tailored against the most recent and common circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants or strains.

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